

VARIATION OF ABSOLUTE VISCOSITY WITH TEMPERATURE.
ORGANIC SOLUTES IN NON-AQUEOUS SOLVENTS

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The viscosity of a fairly large number of systems of non-electrolytes in non-aqueous solvents has been studied at various temperatures. It has been shown that the simple Andrade's equation is applicable to most of the systems. The deviations can be explained by Rabinovich's solvate hypothesis and the depolymerisation hypothesis of Applebey.

The viscosity of a large number of non-electrolytes in non-aqueous solvents has been determined with a view to finding out if Andrade's equation is applicable to these systems. Many workers have applied successfully Andrade's equation to pure liquids and liquid melts. Recently several workers (Berl, Umstätter and Karrer, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1931, **152**, 284; Joshi and Solanki, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940 **17**, 630; Ram Gopal, Ph. D. thesis, 1946. Lucknow University) have extended this equation to aqueous systems.

It has been generally assumed that the failure of the Andrade's equation is due either to the existence of polymerised molecules in the solvents or solvate complexes in the solutions. Another object of this investigation is to find out whether any sudden change in viscosity occurs when the solution passes from the saturated to the supersaturated region.

EXPERIMENTAL

The method employed was that of Chatterji and Ram Gopal (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **24**, 455) which essentially was a modified form of Scarpa's method.

The viscosity was determined with five different concentrations and at several temperatures. But on account of brevity of space, the observations at the highest and the lowest concentrations have only been recorded below. The concentrations are in grams of anhydrous solute in 100 grams of pure solvent.

TABLE I
Viscosity of solutions at different temperatures.

Solvent.	Solute.	Conc.	25°	30°.	35°.	40°	45°.	50°.
Hexane	Naphthalene	15.66	0.003806	0.003636	0.003455	0.003310	0.003166	—
		32.00	—	0.004135	0.003922	0.003737	0.003567	—
,,	Diphenyl-amine	9.83	0.003866	0.003675	0.003515	0.003325	0.003164	—
		33.32	—	0.005085	0.004768	0.004472	0.004182	—
Benzene	Naphthalene.	54.00	0.008712	0.008077	0.007485	0.006983	0.006540	—
		92.00	—	0.009452	0.008742	0.008115	0.007546	—
,,	<i>p</i> -Dibromobenzene	75.60	0.008249	0.007715	0.007190	0.006739	—	—
		90.80	0.008532	0.008051	0.007502	0.007021	—	—
,,	<i>m</i> -Dinitrobenzene	35.12	0.008660	0.008048	0.007465	0.006980	0.006477	—
		66.40	—	0.010540	0.009737	0.009022	0.008286	—
,,	Benzoic acid	3.64	—	0.006414	0.005991	0.005625	0.005267	—
		18.34	—	—	0.006626	0.006220	0.005832	—

TABLE I (contd.).

Solvent.	Solute.	Conc.	25°.	30°.	35°.	40°.	45°.	50°.
Toluene	Naphthalene.	66.00	—	0.007855	0.007470	0.007058	0.006610	0.006270
		82.00	—	—	0.008101	0.007571	0.007105	0.006720
,,	Acenaphthene.	24.50	0.037330	0.006888	0.006467	0.006080	0.005730	—
		40.00	—	0.007940	0.007400	0.006961	0.006516	—
,,	o-Nitrophenol	182.50	—	0.012780	0.011820	0.010880	0.010110	0.009420
		487.00	—	—	0.018380	0.016720	0.015280	0.014110
CCl ₄	Naphthalene.	28.00	—	0.010850	0.010000	0.009335	0.008708	0.008138
		56.45	—	—	—	0.011090	0.010360	0.009672
,,	o-Nitroaniline	1.996	—	0.008952	0.008298	0.007841	0.007321	0.006886
		8.330	—	—	0.010000	0.009361	0.008740	0.008093
CHCl ₃	Acenaphthene	24.20	0.008920	0.008295	0.007764	0.007199	—	—
		34.00	0.009695	0.009070	0.008473	0.007968	—	—
,,	m-Dinitrobenzene	33.32	0.011080	0.010250	0.009550	0.008885	—	—
		40.80	0.012230	0.011370	0.010660	0.009900	—	—
Chlorobenzene	Naphthalene	62.00	—	—	0.009620	0.009041	0.008436	0.007981
		76.00	—	—	0.010110	0.009450	0.008870	0.008320
Bromobenzene	m-Dinitrobenzene	19.40	0.014160	0.013070	0.012210	0.011440	0.010740	—
		39.40	—	0.016750	0.015610	0.014400	0.013430	—
,,	o-Nitrophenol	134.00	—	0.018840	0.017190	0.015760	0.014600	0.013500
		535.00	—	—	0.026580	0.023660	0.021340	0.019340
Aniline	Naphthalene	36.40	—	—	0.023650	0.020920	0.018680	0.016870
		60.00	—	—	0.022240	0.019880	0.01830	0.016160
Nitrobenzene	,,	43.61	—	0.016460	0.015440	0.014400	0.013290	0.012310
		75.11	—	—	0.015780	0.014500	0.013460	0.012520
Acetone	,,	44.83	0.004870	0.004640	0.004428	0.004207	—	—
		68.00	0.005618	0.005296	0.005029	0.004781	—	—
,,	o-Nitroaniline	117.00	0.02290	0.021420	0.020590	0.009826	—	—
		280.00	0.023660	0.021750	0.019940	0.018170	—	—
MeOH	Acenaphthene	2.25	0.005715	0.005301	0.004940	0.004598	0.004360	—
		3.50	—	0.005362	0.005036	0.004714	0.004405	—
,,	Acetanilide	41.05	0.009964	0.009180	0.008461	0.007805	—	—
		53.84	0.011580	0.010570	0.009716	0.008860	—	—
,,	Benzoic acid	68.00	0.013110	0.011960	0.010980	0.010140	0.009466	—
		83.00	—	0.013600	0.012500	0.011470	0.010530	—
,,	Diphenylamine	20.00	0.008140	0.007390	0.006818	0.006313	0.005840	—
		39.40	0.010120	0.009262	0.008495	0.007809	0.007151	—
,,	Urea	20.00	0.009735	0.008914	0.008215	0.007546	0.006923	—
		30.00	0.012220	0.011110	0.010190	0.009311	0.008588	—
Propyl alcohol	Benzoic acid.	40.00	0.028920	0.025310	0.022430	0.019880	0.017700	—
		56.00	—	0.028440	0.024980	0.022060	0.019650	—
,,	Urea	2.56	0.021600	0.018960	0.016910	0.015020	0.013390	—
		4.00	0.022400	0.020030	0.017680	0.015680	0.014010	—
isoPropyl alcohol	p-Dibromobenzene	11.52	0.019450	0.016820	0.014760	0.013070	0.011600	—
		18.00	—	0.016630	0.014700	0.012910	0.011420	—
n-Butyl alcohol	Naphthalene	14.95	—	0.020760	0.018480	0.016330	0.014610	0.013120
		23.00	—	—	0.017960	0.016010	0.014270	0.012800
Acetic acid	,,	15.51	—	0.011870	0.010930	0.010100	0.009386	0.008751
		28.00	—	—	0.01080	0.010240	0.009510	0.008838

DISCUSSION

From the results given above the following types of curves have been plotted: (a) viscosity—temperature, (b) log viscosity—temperature, (c) log viscosity— $1/T$.

I. Benzene-naphthalene
II. MeOH

Of these types of curves, log viscosity against $1/T$ gives a more general and clearer approach to linearity, hence only a few of these curves are given as typical examples. The plotted curves can be divided into two categories: (i) those that give straight lines, (ii) those that do not give straight lines. The results are given below.

TABLE II

Results obtained by plotting log viscosity against $1/T$.

Straight line		Not straight line.	
Solvent.	Solute.	Solvent.	Solute.
1. Toluene	Naphthalene	1. Methyl alcohol	Acenaphthene
2. "	Acenaphthene	2. " "	Acetanilide
3. "	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenol	3. " "	Urea
4. Hexane	Naphthalene	4. " "	Diphenylamine
5. "	Diphenylamine	5. " "	Benzoic acid
6. Benzene	Naphthalene	6. Propyl alcohol	Urea
7. "	<i>p</i> -Dibromobenzene	7. <i>iso</i> Propyl alcohol	<i>p</i> -Dibromobenzene
8. "	<i>m</i> -Dinitrobenzene		
9. "	Benzoic acid		
10. CCl_4	Naphthalene		
11. "	<i>o</i> -Nitroaniline		
12. $CHCl_3$	Acenaphthene		
13. "	<i>m</i> -Dinitrobenzene		
14. Chlorobenzene	Naphthalene		
15. Bromo- "	<i>m</i> -Dinitrobenzene		
16. " "	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenol		
17. Aniline	Naphthalene		
18. Nitrobenzene	"		
19. Acetone	"		
20. Acetic acid	"		
21. Propyl alcohol	Benzoic acid		
22. <i>n</i> -Butyl alcohol	Naphthalene		

From the results it is clear that the substances which dissolve to produce highly viscous solutions show a deviation from the linearity and also the solutions of associated solvents generally do not give a straight line plot except the systems propyl alcohol-benzoic acid, *n*-butyl alcohol-naphthalene.

The simple Andrade's equation $\ln \eta = A + B/T$ meant for non-associated pure liquids is applicable to most of the non-electrolytes in non-associated solvents examined here, which means that the solutions behave almost as non-associated liquids in this respect.

Moreover, when the constants A and B are calculated, the results obtained are almost the same as in aqueous solutions. The value of A is nearly constant and has the same numerical values as those for aqueous solutions, which means that at very high temperatures all solutions, whether aqueous or non-aqueous, approach a constant value for viscosity. Only in those cases, where the solvent has a chance of being associated, such as alcohols, the value of A is slightly higher than the rest. As regards B in non-aqueous solutions, also we find that its value can be put into three categories. The value of B is between (i) 900 and 1500, (ii) 1500 and 2000, (iii) above 2000, as in the case of aqueous solutions of electrolytes. The results of A and B are given in Table III.

TABLE III

Solvent.	Solute.	A .	B (Q/R)	Solvent.	Solute.	A .	B (Q/R).
1. Hexane	Naphthalene	-5.4400	932.3	16. CCl_4	<i>o</i> -Nitro-aniline	-6.6784	1438.0
2. Acetone	"	-5.5391	990.2	17. Acetone	"	-6.6784	1438.0
3. Hexane	Diphenyl-amine	-5.9833	1065.0	18. Methyl-alcohol	Diphenyl-amine	-7.0064	1513.0
4. Toluene	Naphthalene	-5.6413	1092.0	19. "	Benzoic acid	-6.8969	1540.0
5. Chlorobenzene	"	-5.8607	1195.0	20. Acetic acid	Naphthalene	-6.8984	1540.0
6. Toluene	Acenaphthene	-6.0181	1192.0	21. Methyl alcohol	Acetanilide	-7.0876	1557.0
7. Benzene	Benzoic acid	-6.1510	1221.0	22. Toluene	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenol	-7.1260	1642.0
8. "	<i>p</i> -Dibromobenzene	-6.1574	1248.0	23. Bromobenzene	"	-7.1347	1670.0
9. Bromobenzene	<i>m</i> -Dinitrobenzene	-6.2957	1251.0	24. Methyl alcohol	Urea	-7.3713	1642.0
10. Benzene	Naphthalene	-6.4252	1336.0	25. Chloroform	Acenaphthene	-7.6628	1727.0
11. "	<i>m</i> -Dinitrobenzene	-6.4261	1336.0	26. Aniline	Naphthalene	-8.6345	2176.0
12. CCl_4	Naphthalene	-6.3009	1337.0	27. Propyl alcohol	Urea	-9.1434	2291.0
13. Nitrobenzene	"	-6.1363	1354.0	28. "	Benzoic acid	-9.2216	2353.0
14. Methyl alcohol	Acenaphthene	-6.7354	1377.0	29. <i>iso</i> -"	<i>p</i> -Dibromobenzene	-9.4040	2353.0
15. Chloroform	<i>m</i> -Dinitrobenzene	-6.5054	1394.0	30. <i>n</i> -Butyl alcohol	Naphthalene	-9.4060	2385.0

To the first two categories the Andrade's equation is applicable, except for a few alcoholic solutions, as they give a straight line plot for log viscosity against $1/T$. The substances of the second category having the value of B between 1500 and 2000 show a tendency of forming solvates. Greater solvation will require greater shearing stress and therefore the value of B is large in the second category than in the first where the viscosity is low. In category three, the viscosity is considerably high and therefore the value of B is correspondingly high.

The system benzoic acid-propyl alcohol gives a comparatively high linear relation than benzoic acid in methyl alcohol. This may be due to two reasons, firstly the association in propyl alcohol is less than in methyl alcohol, secondly benzoic acid may be able to depolymerise the slightly associated propyl alcohol, but not methyl alcohol, which is more associated.